

IMP

BOX

DELIVERABLE REPORT

WP2 Dissemination, communication,
exploitation

D2.2

Project Website

H2020-SC1-2020-Single-Stage-RTD Project N° 965173

WP Leader: **Promoscience**

Due date of deliverable: **30/06/2021 (M3)**

Actual submission month: **Month 3**

PROJECT DETAILS

PROJECT ACRONYM	PROJECT TITLE
Imptox	An innovative analytical platform to investigate the effect and toxicity of micro and nano plastics combined with environmental contaminants on the risk of allergic disease in preclinical and clinical studies
GRANT AGREEMENT NO:	FUNDING SCHEME
965173	H2020-EU.3.1.1. - Understanding health, wellbeing and disease SC1-BHC-36-2020 - Micro- and nano-plastics in our environment:
START DATE	Understanding exposures and impacts on human health
01/04/2021	

IMPTOX CONSORTIUM

1. University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry (UBFC), Republic of Serbia, coordinator
2. Moverim Consulting Sprl (MOVERIM), Belgium, partner
3. Promoscience srl (Promoscience), Italy, partner
4. Medizinische Universitaet Wien (MUW), Austria, partner
5. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KU Leuven), Belgium, partner
6. Ghent University (UGent), Belgium, partner
7. Karolinska Institutet (KI), Sweden, partner
8. University of Vienna (UNIVIE), Austria, partner
9. SCIENSANO (Sciensano), Belgium, partner
10. Centre for Functional and Evolutionary Ecology (CNRS), France, partner
11. Srebrnjak Children’s Hospital (SCH), Croatia, partner
12. Haute Ecole Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale (HES-SO), Switzerland, partner

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

DELIVERABLE ID	TITLE
D2.2	Project Website
CONTRIBUTING WORK PACKAGE	ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE
WP 2: Dissemination, communication, exploitation	30/06/2021
PERSON RESPONSIBLE FOR THE DELIVERABLE	
Riccardo Brancaleon (Promoscience)	
NATURE	
R - Report	
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to other programme participants & EC: (Specify) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group (Specify) <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

REPORT DETAILS

ACTUAL SUBMISSION DATE

30/06/2021

NUMBER OF PAGES

12

FOR MORE INFO PLEASE CONTACT

Riccardo Brancaleon
 Promoscience srl
 +39 040 3755690
 Area Science Park - Edificio E3
 Padriciano, 99 - 34149 Trieste
 Italy

email:
 riccardo.brancaleon@promoscience.com

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	DESCRIPTION / REASON FOR MODIFICATION	STATUS
1	25/06/2021	Riccardo Brancaleon		Final
				Choose an item.
				Choose an item.
				Choose an item.
				Choose an item.
				Choose an item.

CONTENTS

Project Summary	4
Work package 2 – Main Aims & Tasks	4
The project website – A communication Tool	5
Website description	5
Landing Page	6
The Project	7
The Workplan	7
Synergies in Action – Outreach & Guidance	9
The Consortium	10
How to contact us	11
Partner restricted intranet	12
Further Steps	12

PROJECT SUMMARY

Despite the abundant and ubiquitous presence of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), knowledge on their prevalence and potentially harmful effects on human health are limited. The Imptox project aims to fill this gap by providing innovative solutions and approaches for evaluating MNP impact on the environment and food chain, their presence in animals and plants, and their effect on human allergy and asthma.

MNP surfaces may attract and retain hazardous contaminants such as metals, allergens, pathogenic bacteria and toxins, and deliver them into the body. Therefore, Imptox will focus on the effects of MNPs combined with contaminants to evaluate whether ingested and inhaled MNPs augments allergic disease. Imptox will develop novel tools to identify, extract, characterize, and quantify MNPs from food, the environment, and in exposed animals, focusing on assessing MNP prevalence based on size, shape and type. Labelled MNPs will be used to evaluate MNP fate, accumulation, toxicity in pre-clinical studies, and clinical research will investigate the relationship between MNP exposure and allergic disease in children.

Imptox scientific data will provide a basis for policy discussions at the national and European level on human health hazards and risks, food safety, use of plastic food packaging materials, MNP levels in drinking water and water used for crop irrigation, dietary advice for patients with allergic disease, respiratory health and others.

WORK PACKAGE 2 – MAIN AIMS & TASKS

The overall objective of WP 2 is to effectively **communicate** project ideas and activities carried out within the scope of the project to different target audiences, to **disseminate** results and to **transfer knowledge** to policymakers and stakeholders so they can act on it.

More specifically, WP 2 aims to disseminate the project's outputs by addressing a large variety of actors potentially interested in Imptox's results as well as to exploit results by submitting recommendations to policy makers, thereby transferring evidence-based knowledge to decision makers for the purpose of better governance. Furthermore, various routes to assure scientific advancement will be routinely explored through the publication of e.g. SOPs, technical notes or through commercial exploitation.

In order to reach the objectives set in work-package two, various tasks will be carried out:

- A communication and dissemination plan will be established defining target-oriented communication and dissemination actions.
- The following tools have been identified through which to communicate with the target audience:
 - o A strong project identity and logo
 - o The **project's website** which will be explained in detail further down in this report.
 - o A Communication Kit, including a corporate presentation, leaflet, poster, a roll-up and others.
 - o Social Media

- With the tools provided in this work-package, communication and dissemination activities will be implemented by establishing and pursuing relationships with the media through press releases, tailor-made press-kits, appealing infographics, etc. Furthermore, to help promote awareness about Imptox, social media channels will be activated. A dialogue with stakeholder groups will be established for the purpose of networking activities and partners will be encouraged to take part in scientific conferences as well as calls for articles in scientific journals. A final event will be held in the form of an international conference and networking event.
- The impact of communication activities will be traced and analysed through a monitoring tool.
- The project's results will be made available to stakeholders and policymakers in a reserved area of the webpage through a final online report summarising the outcomes. In close collaboration with the JRC, the project's outcomes will contribute to the definition of relevant guidance documents to regarding MNPs and health. Finally, in order to protect new analytical approaches, a patent search and market analysis will be carried out.

THE PROJECT WEBSITE – A COMMUNICATION TOOL

The present deliverable describes the results achieved within Task 2.2. “Communication Tools”. This task aims at developing a website to facilitate both, internal communication among the consortium members through a partner-only section, as well as external communication with stakeholders, the media and the general public. The website will support the work package leader and the members of the consortium throughout all three main tasks of this work-package: communication, dissemination and exploitation.

WEBSITE DESCRIPTION

The website currently provides an overview of the project all in one page to be scrolled up and down. This solution allows visitors to navigate through different sections of the website seamlessly, accessing all contents.

Fonts, colours and graphical elements on the website are chosen to assure coherence and to underline the project's visual identity.

Scrolling down from the landing page, the visitor gets to the following sections: the project, the workplan, synergies in action, outreach and guidance, the Imptox team and how to contact us, with a news section currently being set up. At the very end of the page, reference to the grant agreement number and the EU Horizon 2020 funding is visible. While these features are already fully functional, the website will be updated and further refined in the next months.

Landing Page

The Imptox website is responsive, which means it has been set up to automatically adjust and optimize the viewing experience according to the device used: a personal computer, a mobile telephone, a tablet, or a laptop. This makes the online text easy to read, and offers the most suitable navigation mode for each device as well as an optimal layout for each screen resolution. An example of different viewing options on different devices is provided here:

The Project

This section highlights the innovative character of the Imptox project, focusing on the following three elements:

- The development of new tools to measure and characterise MNPs
- To research MNPs in combination with pollutants latching on to their surfaces
- The relationship between MNPs and allergic diseases

Each one of those elements is presented in a circle which intersects with the others, symbolizing the interrelatedness among those research elements.

The Workplan

The workplan section is set up in the form of a carousel where visitors are invited to click on an arrow to explore more steps of the Imptox workplan. They can move back and forth between different areas of the workplan pushing arrows to go ahead or to go back. For each part of the plan, images have been created by Promoscience's in-house designer that best transmit the content of each step graphically, while also being in line with the visual identity of Imptox. The stages of the workplan on the website include the following:

- MNPs in Food and Air
- New Tools
- MNPs and Contaminants
- In vitro e in vivo testing
- Clinical Studies

THE WORKPLAN

1 MNPS IN FOOD AND AIR

We plan to identify and characterise MNPs in a variety of foods, plants and in coastal air samples.

THE WORKPLAN

2 NEW TOOLS

We aim to develop and optimise analytical tools for MNP detection and characterisation beyond the current state-of-the-art. Open-source software based on machine learning will help speed that process up.

THE WORKPLAN

3 MNPS AND CONTAMINANTS

We intend to generate new knowledge on MNPs as carriers of common pathogens, heavy metals, and allergens.

THE WORKPLAN

4 IN VITRO AND IN VIVO TESTING

We will carry out studies on the impact of model MNPs and MNPs plus contaminants in vitro and in vivo.

THE WORKPLAN

5 CLINICAL STUDIES

We will conduct clinical studies with children living in cities and by the seaside to determine links between MNP exposure and food allergy.

Synergies in Action – Outreach & Guidance

In these two sections more can be learned about the collaboration of Imptox with non-consortium members. In the section “Synergies in Action”, reference is made to Imptox’s participation in CUSP, The European Research Cluster to Understand the Health Impacts of Micro- and Nanoplastics. In “Outreach & Guidance”, the importance of Imptox to collaborate with policymakers, stakeholders, NGOs and civil society is stressed and the aim to provide decision makers with data on which to base decisions so as to safeguard health and environment is highlighted.

SYNERGIES IN ACTION

Imptox is one of five projects in the EU Horizon 2020 programme that will work together with the European Commission's Joint Research Center to form a cluster on MNPs and Health. It is the cluster's overall goal to contribute with new scientific knowledge and know-how to the European Strategy for Plastics.

OUTREACH & GUIDANCE

Imptox partners plan to work closely with Non-Governmental Organizations, stakeholders from industry, business, scientists and policymakers. We plan to deliver data and its ramifications to help decision makers, risk assessors and regulators safeguard our air, water and food supply.

The Consortium

This section briefly introduces the project team, composed of 12 partner institutions visually distributed on a world map. This is then followed by a list of the consortium partners, represented by their acronyms and logos. Visitors will be able to click on each partner and access some basic information about each institutions and retrieve details about the persons who work on the project. This function is currently not yet available, but will be so within the next two weeks.

How to contact us

The last part of the website appearing on the bottom provides a contact email address for anyone who has further questions or wants to get involved to be able to get in touch with Imptox. An ad-hoc email address secretariat@imptox.eu has been configured to which Promoscience has access. Depending on the nature of the message received, Promoscience will then forward it on to the right contact person within the consortium. The bottom of the page also acknowledges the source of funding thanks to which this project has been brought to life, specifying the grant agreement number 965173 and the European Commission's Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon2020.

HOW TO CONTACT US

by email

secretariat@imptox.eu

The Imptox project has received funding from the EU's H2020 framework program for research and innovation under grant agreement n. 965173

Partner restricted intranet

The website includes a partner-restricted area, the Imptox intranet, which is accessible from the public website through a username and password. While this section serves project coordination purposes given its document and project management functionalities, it is also connected to Task 2.6. "Online Report Publication" and to Milestones M2 "Implementation of SLM online tool for data management" and MS5 "Innovation management processes (including knowledge and IPR)".

Further Steps

These tasks will be concluded within the next 14 days

- News Section
- Fully developed partner-section with profiles of each involved institution and the people working on the Imptox project

